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Biogas Purification by Methane and Acetate Manufacturing

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ABSTRACT

Wastewater treatment plants have two persistent financial and energetic drains, the carbon dioxide content of biogas, which limits its commercial sale, and the presence of trace organics in the wastewater effluent, which damages the aquatic ecosystem, like the Great Barrier Reef. Biogas is a renewable methane resource that is underutilized due to the variable CO₂ content (~40%). Biogas is energy intensive to purify and limited by the economy of scale (> 8.85 GJ/h) to large-scale purification methods, thus small-scale processes require development. Electrocatalytic microbes native to wastewater have been shown to convert CO₂ to CH₄ and acetate, however complete conversion of the CO₂ content to CH₄ is energy intensive. Here we show a low power bioelectrochemical fuel cell design to purify biogas to pipeline quality methane (98%), manufacture methane and/or acetate, and remove trace organics, using HCO₃⁻ as the transport charge carrier from dissolved CO₂ from the biogas through an anion exchange membrane. This decreased the power required to separate CO₂ from methane in biogas on a molar basis, resulting in a net energy recovery similar to current industrial systems. Magnesium anode use resulted in an energy positive system. Tests evaluated the influence of cathode potential on the current density, HCO₃⁻ ion flux and the rates and efficiencies of methane production, resulting in optimization at -0.7V versus standard hydrogen electrode (SHE). A techno-economic analysis modeled a positive return on investment for scaled-up production to purify small biogas streams that are otherwise financially unrecoverable. Carbon sequestration by production of methane, acetate and solid fertilizers demonstrated profitable and energy efficient waste-to-resource conversion.

1 | Introduction

A bioelectrochemical system (BES) makes use of microbes at an electrode surface as “electrocatalysts” for reduction and oxidation reactions. Electroactive biofilms are capable of the bioelectrosynthesis of chemicals that are otherwise too complex or expensive for electrosynthesis. Electroactive biofilm microbes are ubiquitous, naturally present in wastewater and self-regenerate. Present uses focus on cleaning dilute wastewaters and producing high value chemicals from waste streams. Biofilms outperform traditional biological methods at low concentrations and produce less biomass, thus reducing disposal costs.

Biogas is a global methane resource produced from a variety of systems, including organic waste treatment systems (Tilche and Galatola 2008). Biogas is underutilized due to the high and variable content of carbon dioxide (~40%), which is energy intensive to separate. Small-scale biogas purification is limited by the economy of scale, causing the resource to go unused (flared) in many smaller wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). The variable methane content of biogas requires purification to pipeline grade natural gas specification (98% methane) to receive market sale value. The most common commercial approach for biogas purification is physio-chemical carbon dioxide, CO₂, removal, including pressure swing

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adsorption (PSA), membrane separation, and “scrubbing” with water, amines, or organic solvents (Bauer et al. 2013; Urban 2009).

The methane content of biogas is a result of the energy available to the microbes during anaerobic digestion, not their metabolic limits (Ferry 1993); thus, supplying methanogens with additional energy can produce pure methane (Bauer et al. 2013). Biological biogas purification (biomethanation) adds hydrogen to biologically convert all the CO_2 to CH_4 . The drawback is high energy use for hydrogen gas production. Electromethanogenesis is the bioelectrocatalytic production of CH_4 from CO_2 without intermediate hydrogen and requires less energy than electrolysis, -0.241 V standard hydrogen electrode (SHE) versus -0.414 V respectively (Bassani et al. 2015; Kambara et al. 2023; Luo and Angelidaki 2012; Martin et al. 2013; Tartakovsky et al. 2014; Van Eerten-Jansen et al. 2011). In this paper, we examine the separation of CO_2 and hydrogen sulfide, H_2S , from biogas using a BES based on an anion exchange membrane (AEM) that uses dissolved CO_2 , HCO_3^- , as the transport charge carrier, thereby removing CO_2 physio-chemically. The BES simultaneously converts $1/9$ mol CO_2 to CH_4 via electromethanogenesis. Dual transport and conversion of less CO_2 via electromethanogenesis requires less energy, making the BES energetically superior. The techno-economic analysis and experimental results for methane production efficiencies and HCO_3^- anion transport rates support the BES as an alternative to current biogas purification technologies for small biogas streams (< 8.85 GJ/h) that are otherwise financially unrecoverable, such as for remote communities, military installations, intensive farming, and solid waste management facilities powering fleet vehicles.

The wastewater treatment plants of Brisbane, on the Pacific Coast of Australia, have been fitted with the best available technology for the minimization of sludge, using the Cambi thermal hydrolysis process. Figure 1 demonstrates the process flow diagram of a wastewater treatment plant with a bioelectrochemical system in the standard position for biogas purification. Waste sludge is hydrolysed and fermented. The organic rich effluent from the Cambi is mixed with a stream of anaerobic digestion (AD) effluent at a steady concentration and fed to the anode of a microbial BES. Biogas is fed to the cathode with anaerobic digester effluent. The liquid effluent organics of both anode and cathode are of equivalent or lower concentration than the

anaerobic digester effluent and appropriate for combination with, and continued treatment of, anaerobic digester effluent.

Figure 2 shows the cathodic mechanisms for electromethanogenesis, either direct or indirect reduction of CO_2 . The mechanism determines the operating potential and energy input required for methane production. Direct electromethanogenesis reduces CO_2 with H^+ and electrons to CH_4 ($E'_0 = -0.24$ V) (a). Direct electroacetogenesis reduces CO_2 with H^+ and electrons to acetate, followed by acetotrophic methanogenesis ($E'_0 = -0.28$ V) (b). Biocatalysed electrolysis reduces H^+ from water and electrons to H_2 , followed by hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis ($E'_0 = -0.41$ V) (c). Inorganic electrolysis can occur, followed by hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis ($>> E'_0 = -0.41$ V) (c). Direct formate production reduces CO_2 with H^+ and electrons to formate, followed by methanogenesis ($< E'_0 = -0.41$ V) (not shown). Direct electromethanogenesis uses the least energy, with the lowest negative potential and has been the subject of intense research (Rotaru et al. 2014; Villano et al. 2010). The mechanism has been proven for one methanogen species, which accepts electrons directly from electroactive geobacter bacteria fed on ethanol (Rotaru et al. 2014) and is probable on a graphite cathode (Gregory, Bond, and Lovley 2004). Indirect electromethanogenesis reduces CO_2 to a chemical intermediate, such as acetate, formate or hydrogen, and then to methane (b, c). Direct electroacetogenesis could lead to the transport of the intermediate acetate (or formate) as a charge carrier instead of acetotrophic methanogenesis, which reduces the methane coulombic efficiency. All electromethanogenesis mechanisms reduce the energy requirement to less than electrolysis. Microbiomes may transfer electrons via membrane-bound cytochromes, nanowires, and/or their Extracellular Polymeric Substance, EPS, a negatively charged conducting biopolymer (Bard 2001; Palecek and Wang 2005) connecting them to the electrode and each other. Electrocatalysis is the microbe's sole energy/food source, save trace nutrients. For additional electrode-microbe interactions, interested readers are referred to the works of Nevin et al. (2011) and Rabaey and Rozendal (2010).

Biogas flows continuously into the cathode solution. AD effluent flows continuously into the anode and is added to maintain the cathode volume, 6:9 $\text{H}_2\text{O}:\text{CO}_2$. Methane has a low solubility and passes through the cathode solution while CO_2 (and any H_2S) solubilizes with water into HCO_3^- (and HS^-) and acts as

FIGURE 1 | Process diagram of wastewater treatment system: Biogas purification by a bioelectrochemical system, including anaerobic digestion, fermentation and biogas purification of CO_2 , CH_4 , and H_2S .

FIGURE 2 | BES design and process flow diagram with mass and energy balance. Cathode shows methane production by direct and indirect bioelectrocatalysis methods. Purifying biogas requires bicarbonate transport of 8:1 $\text{HCO}_3^-:\text{CH}_4$, decreasing the amount of CO_2 to be converted into methane by the microbes and therefore the power required. Pure methane output is a mix of purified input methane and newly manufactured methane. Anode shows three separate options.

the charge carrier through the AEM. Inefficient reduction gives the cathode slightly basic conditions, ideal for absorbing CO_2 . Inefficient oxidation gives the anode slightly acidic conditions, ideal for desorbing CO_2 . The transported HCO_3^- is acidified in the anode to CO_2 gas and comes out of solution. The HCO_3^- acts as a pH buffer in both the cathode and anode. To balance the charge and maintain electroneutrality, 8 HCO_3^- ions must transfer through the AEM for every 1 HCO_3^- reduced to CH_4 , resulting in pure methane at minimal energy use (mole basis). Transport of HCO_3^- decreases the amount of CO_2 that must be converted to CH_4 to purify biogas by 8/9ths, thereby decreasing the energy required to 1/9th that of biomethanation designs, which convert all the CO_2 to CH_4 (Bassani et al. 2015; Luo and Angelidaki 2012; Martin et al. 2013; Tartakovsky et al. 2014; Van Eerten-Jansen et al. 2011). The dissolved H_2S (HS^-) will pass through the AEM to be acidified and gasified back into H_2S in the anode and scrubbed from the anode gas.

Wastewater bioelectrocatalysis began development by removing organic chemical oxygen demand (COD) from wastewater to concentrations lower than anaerobic digesters with anodic microbiomes at efficiencies of >80% (Mukimin and Vistanty 2023; Rozendal et al. 2008a; Rozendal et al. 2008b). Microbe species require a specific range of applied electrode potential and environmental conditions. Biofilms in a typical BES are colonized by microbes common to anaerobic digestion, including acetoanaerobium and electrocatalytic geobacter (Rabaey and Rozendal 2010). Research on cathodic bioelectrosynthesis has focused on producing value added chemicals from waste streams (Harnisch and Schroeder 2010), including methane from municipal wastewater (Clauwaert et al. 2008; Noori et al. 2020; Reddy et al. 2022; Villano et al. 2010). Electrocatalytic microbiomes can lessen the over-potential of hydrogen electrolysis ($E'_0 = -0.414\text{ V}$) using mixed communities of electroactive bacteria and syntrophic methanogens, for example with electroactive geobacter and

syntrophic methanosarcina (Morita et al. 2011). Methane intermediates have been biocatalytically produced at potentials less negative than hydrogen electrolysis including; acetate (Marshall 2013; Nevin et al. 2011), formate (Nevin et al. 2011) and hydrogen (Clauwaert et al. 2008; Morozov et al. 2002; Tartakovsky et al. 2014; Van Eerten-Jansen et al. 2011; Villano et al. 2011). Methane electrosynthesis occurs over the potential range $\sim -0.3\text{ V}$ to -0.9 V (Table S1). Electroacetogenesis occurs at less negative potentials, $\sim -0.4\text{ V}$ (Nevin et al. 2011), indicating there is a transition of the product spectrum with the change in negative potential from primarily volatile fatty acids to methane with biocatalytic hydrogen as the intermediate. Biohydrogen is the most common intermediate with mixed communities giving the highest current densities ($>4.1\text{ A/m}^2$) (Cheng, Ho, and Cord-Ruwisch 2011; Van Eerten-Jansen et al. 2013) and coulombic efficiencies (50%–99%) (Call, Wagner, and Logan 2009; Rozendal et al. 2008a; Rozendal et al. 2008b; Villano et al. 2010) because anaerobic digestion microbiomes have evolved to work symbiotically (Noori et al. 2020). This implies indirect electromethanogenesis is a common mechanism in nature. This was one of the first investigations of biogas purification or acetate production using single chamber AEMs for HCO_3^- ion transfer for a high rate methane producing BES to demonstrate economic viability (Aryal et al. 2021). Cation exchange membranes (CEM) are commonly used (Harnisch, Schroeder, and Scholz 2008; Rozendal, Hamelers, and Buisman 2006) due to the lower solution resistance for the transport of cations or protons (H^+ ion channeling) (Sleutels et al. 2009). AEMs are effective for OH^- ion transfer in bioelectrolysis cells to buffer pH gradients (Fornero et al. 2010; Sleutels et al. 2009; Torres, Lee, and Rittmann 2008) and HCO_3^- ion transfer in electrodialysis at ambient and high pressure (1390 A/m^2) (Eisaman et al. 2011). Drawbacks include anion intermediates in methanogenesis (ex. volatile fatty acids (VFAs), formate and acetate) can be lost due to non-selective transport and reduce methane coulombic

efficiency or reversibly foul the membrane (Strathmann 2004). Benefits of AEM will include high pressure operation which will improve reaction rates and economic feasibility.

Electroactive biofilms experience pH stress at the electrode surface. To avoid pH stress, biofilms form thick layers of conductive EPS far from the pH gradient (Jones and Buie 2019). Biofilm porosity and channel size are affected by the electron transfer mechanism (Renslow et al. 2013), growth conditions, and shear rate, which increases metabolic growth rates to form thicker biofilms capable of withstanding this shear stress. Biofilm attachment is negatively affected by long-term high shear stress. Biofilm growth optimization occurs at higher shear (~1.0 Pa) and then with decreased shear for steady-state operation with convection of a well buffered solution to enhance diffusion.

Wastewater biofilms operate for >50 years, where constant contact with wastewater bacteria enhances self-regeneration. Electroactive biofilms in wastewater treatment have shown steady, high efficiency (99%) and long-term stability (1.5 years) (Ge and He 2016; Liang et al. 2018; Yan et al. 2019). An electroactive biofilm for wastewater treatment will self-regenerate and provide stable operation continuously, if in constant contact with wastewater bacteria (Baudler, Riedl, and Schröder 2014; Gajda et al. 2020; Ge and He 2016; Jones and Buie 2019; Liang et al. 2018; Lu et al. 2017).

2 | Methods

2.1 | Bio-Electrochemical System Test Methods

An acrylic plate and frame reactor was packed with 2–6 mm diameter graphite granules (El Carb 100, Graphite Sales Inc., USA) with graphite rods as current collectors (12 cm long, 7 mm diameter). A minimally gas permeable anion exchange membrane (AMX-7001S from Membranes International Inc., 14 cm × 12 cm) was compressed between the plates with rubber gaskets sealed with adhesive (Villano et al. 2011). The catholyte was saturated with sodium bicarbonate and maintained saturation by continuous CO₂ gas sparging (36 mM CO₂). Gas exchange occurred in a Schott bottle (1156 mL) with a drip to avoid bubble resistance on the electrode during CO₂ absorption. The drip electrically isolated the pH probes from current in the electrolyte; reducing pH probe signal noise. The gas volume included a 100 mL syringe inverted in silicone oil to maintain pressure (1 atm). The bottle served multiple purposes: for pH measurement, gas and liquid sampling, and temperature control in a water bath at 30°C. Current densities are reported using the membrane surface area.

The carbon electrode granules and rods were soaked for 24 h in 1 M HCl, 1 M NaOH and rinsed with deionized (DI) water. The empty compartment volumes were 336 mL each. The liquid volume was 157 mL, giving 47% vol. void fraction.

The electrolyte for both compartments was 36 mM HCO₃⁻ in 64 mM phosphate buffer (6 g/L Na²HPO₄, 3 g/L KH₂PO₄), macronutrients (0.5 g/L NH₄Cl, 0.5 g/L NaCl, 0.1 g/L MgCl₂·6H₂O, 15 mg/L CaCl₂), and micronutrients (1.5 mg/L FeCl₃·6H₂O,

0.15 mg/L H₃BO₃, 0.03 mg/L CuSO₄·5H₂O, 0.18 mg/L KI, 0.12 mg/L MnCl₂·4H₂O, 0.06 mg/L Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, 0.12 mg/L ZnSO₄·7H₂O, 0.15 mg/L CoCl₂·6H₂O, 10 mg/L EDTA acidic form, and 0.023 mg/L NiCl₂·6H₂O). Chlorine salt concentrations were kept low to maximize HCO₃⁻ absorption and avoid chlorine gas formation on the anode. Electrolytic systems generate pH gradients at the electrode surface that require neutralization. The electrolyte pH was maintained by the constant 36 mM HCO₃⁻ (dissolved CO₂ gas at saturation) and phosphate buffer between pH 6.5–7.5 ± 0.1 and monitored continuously (TPS pH probes and meters). The electrolyte recirculated at 90 mL/min.

Coulombic efficiency is the efficiency of the charge (electrons) in the products versus the charge transferred in/out of the system. Product yields were sampled in triplicate and coulombic efficiencies were calculated using a mass balance equation with the gas composition in mole % for CO₂, CH₄, and H₂ (checked for Cl₂); VFA concentration in ppm; and liquid and gas volumes assuming ideal behavior (Bard and Faulkner 2001). To ensure significant measurement of the CH₄ produced by the microorganisms, the feed gas did not include additional CH₄ due to the lower detection limit of the gas chromatographs (Shimadzu GC-8A and Perkin Elmer GC-TCD, 50 ppmv). Biogas contains high concentrations of CH₄ (~60%), which could influence the microorganism's reaction kinetics. This would be an appropriate follow up study c.

The coulombic efficiency of transport is the carbon transported compared to the charge supplied. Transport rate is the moles of HCO₃⁻ and desorbed CO₂ that cross the AEM from cathode to anode (moles/m²/day). Transport efficiency is the percent of transported HCO₃⁻ and CO₂ compared to the inlet mass flow measured using gas concentrations, TIC/TOC, pH and conductivity per liquid volume (%mol CO₂/m³/day). Transport phenomena and efficiencies are not ion specific and affected by salt ions.

Liquid phase volatile fatty acids (VFA) in both compartments were measured using a Shimadzu Prominence High Pressure Liquid Chromatograph (HPLC) with a detection limit of 2 ppm to measure ethanol, propanol, n-butanol, acetic acid, propionic acid, iso-butyric acid, butyric acid, iso-valeric acid, valeric acid, hexanoic acid, and periodically measured dissolved methane, formate, lactic acid, glycerol, and propanediol. Total inorganic and organic carbon were measured with an Analytik Jena multi N/C 2100S Total Organic Carbon Analyser.

The cathode was characterized before and after inoculation and tests by cyclic voltammetry (CV) with and without dissolved CO₂ to observe the development of biocatalysis and identify the formal potential of hydrogen evolution. The applied cathode potential was scanned from +0.2 V to -0.8 V or -1 V with scan rates of 1, 5, and 10 mV/s using a VersaSTAT 3 (Princeton Applied Research, USA) with respect to a 3 M KCl Ag/AgCl reference electrode in the cathode (+0.205 V SHE; ProSense QiS, The Netherlands). The cell voltage was recorded using an Agilent 34970A data acquisition unit. Biotic potentiostatic tests ranged from -0.550 to -0.800 V and increased by -50 mV without randomization to ensure the microbiome was reducing CO₂ without abiotic hydrogen gas. The reactor was acclimated for 1 week after each potential step.

Then, the methane yield was measured for 5 days and calculated using data after 24 h. The reactor ran for 12 days/test with duplicates totaling > 144 days, not including incubation (~6 weeks). Abiotic potentiostatic tests ranged from -0.500 to -0.800 V to determine the abiotic hydrogen electrolysis yield and HCO_3^- flux during steady state, which was achieved in ~1 h. Potentials are reported versus SHE. Energy efficiency is the product of coulombic and voltage efficiency. Voltage efficiency was calculated using the Gibbs free energy of methane oxidation, 890.4 kJ/mol.

The cathodic electroactive biofilm was cultivated with a mix of methanogens using eight grams of anaerobic sludge from an upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB Reactor) (Luggage Point, Australia) and anode effluent microbes from an MFC consuming acetate, which switched polarity. The cathode was maintained at 1 mA for 1 month and 2 mA for another 2 weeks. Weekly catholyte replacements removed planktonic cells ensuring only biofilm growth and minimized membrane clogging (Characklis et al. 1982). All sample measurements have 5% error or less.

2.2 | Techno-Economic Analysis Model Method

A techno-economic analysis (TEA) was performed to determine the capital and operating costs for purifying biogas in a BES model (Coulson et al. 2006). See Table S3 for further information. For these calculations, the BES was assumed to have 95% coulombic efficiency on the cathode and anode, based on this work. Based on literature, the model BES operated at 10 A/m^2 (Aelterman et al. 2006; Foley et al. 2010; Rabaey and Verstraete 2005) and the membrane operated at a maximum 50 A/m^2 (Membranes International 2018). Table 1 shows the mass and energy balance of the methane and acetate BES models. The cathode consumed CO_2 at -0.9 V, the anode consumed wastewater COD (acetate) at -0.2 V (Rabaey and Rozendal 2010) including overpotentials. These were non-spontaneous reactions (negative Gibbs free energy) and required energy input. The BES processed $100 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$ biogas ($67:33 \text{ CH}_4:\text{CO}_2$) from a UASB operating at $1000 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ wastewater and 2300 g/m^3 COD (Tchobanoglous 2003) (p. 1012). The membrane surface area was 662 m^2 . The electrolyte volumes were ~ 35 m^3 each, assuming HCO_3^- saturation. The porous electrode was a maximum thickness 5.28 cm , $5.28 \text{ cm}^3/1 \text{ cm}^2$ membrane. Shorter distances were achieved with higher surface area electrodes. The anode was fed 3.05 gCOD/s with a mixed stream from the UASB effluent and Cambi fermenter (pre-UASB). The energy requirement of pump operation was 0.1 kW/m^3 (Foley et al. 2010) and $75.8 \text{ kWh/Nm}^3/\text{h}$ to compress the pure methane gas from 100 to 750 kPa (GPSA 2004).

The chemical and energy prices used were the Australian and world averages for 2023. For electricity, the Australian wholesale average price for 2023 was 53.4 USD\$/MWh (AEMO 2024) which was lower than the US average of 78.8 USD\$/MWh (US EIA 2024). The wholesale price of compressed methane worldwide averaged 7.4 USD\$/GJ (7.5 USD\$/MMBTU), the same as Australian wholesale price (AER 2024; IGU 2024). The sale price of compressed CO_2 (99.95% food grade) was 0.056 USD\$/kg. The wholesale price of acetic acid was 0.584 USD\$/kg (Kelley 2024).

TABLE 1 | Mass and energy balance for model BES at 10 A/m^2 purifying biogas while producing either additional methane or acetate (captured after transport).

	Methane BES	Acetate BES
Flow in		
Biogas (mol/s) (67:33 $\text{CH}_4:\text{CO}_2$)	1.16	1.16
CH_4 (mol/s)	0.77	0.77
CO_2 (mol/s)	0.39	0.39
H_2O (mol/s)	0.26	0.23
Wastewater COD (acetate) (mol/s)	0.05	0.04
Wastewater COD (acetate) (gCOD/s)	3.05	2.75
CH_4 produced by electromethanogenesis (mol/s)	0.04	
CH_3COOH produced by electroacetogenesis (mol/s)		0.04
Cathode e- consumed (mol/s)	0.36	0.32
Cathode Amps (95% CE)	34,800	31,400
Cathode voltage (V)	0.90	0.60
Cathode power (kW)	31.4	18.8
Cell voltage at 10 A/m^2 (V)	0.70	0.40
Power added to cathode (kW)	24.4	12.5
Transport through membrane		
HCO_3^- (mol/s)	0.34	0.30
CH_3COOH (mol/s)		0.04
Flow out		
CH_4 (mol/s)	0.81	0.77
CH_3COOH (mol/s) (captured)		0.04
CO_2 (mol/s)	0.39	0.35
H_2O (mol/s)	0.26	0.26
Anode e- produced (mol/s)	0.38	0.34
Anode Amps (95% CE)	36,700	33,000
Anode voltage (V)	0.20	0.20
Anode power (kW)	7.0	6.3

Location factors are significant when assessing the economic potential. Membrane price was 160 USD\$/ m^2 (Inc. 2024). Electrode prices are listed in Table S2. The electrode surface

areas are dependent on electroactive surface area. Operating costs included maintenance. Hydrogen sulfite gas is automatically dissolved as HS⁻ and removed from the biogas along with the CO₂ via transport to the anode, where it is regasified as H₂S. Capital costs did not include sulfite removal from the CO₂ anode gas stream or acetate concentration (flash column).

Electricity from the cathode was purchased from the grid and electricity from anode was sold. The hardware supporting an off-grid BES included an inverter (40%–60% efficiency), a transformer (90% efficiency) and a rectifier (0.6V to power). However, rectifier losses are large compared to the system's voltage, 0.6 V out of ≥0.9V. The payback period, cash flow, net present and return on investment were calculated using Equations (1)–(3):

$$\text{Payback Period} = \text{Revenue} * t - \text{FCC} - \text{FOC} * \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Cash Flow} = \frac{\text{Revenue} - \text{FOC}}{(1 + \text{discount rate})^t} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Net Present Value} = -\text{FCC} + \sum_0^t \text{Cash Flow} \quad (3)$$

3 | Results and Discussion

Methane was successfully produced and CO₂ was removed from biogas using two simultaneous cathode reactions and three separate anodic reactions, as previously reviewed in the BES design (Figure 2). Acetate oxidation was successful, however it allowed acetate back diffusion through the AEM, disrupting the carbon balance calculations and was discontinued. Acetate COD oxidation requires additional electron volts to reduce CO₂ to methane (~–0.2V). Magnesium dissolution was highly successful and resulted in an energy (generating) independent system. However, it resulted in MgCO₃ precipitate blockages in the liquid lines and the decision was made to discontinue its use. Solid magnesium oxidation produced magnesium carbonate and/or struvite (fertilizers) by precipitation (–2.37V). Solid fertilizers are profitable and save resources by reducing agricultural runoff (Molinos-Senante et al. 2011; Ueno and Fujii 2001). Water oxidation provided the most accurate carbon balance and was used exclusively for research purposes. Oxygen back-diffusion from the anode can inhibit methanogenesis (Abdollahi et al. 2022; Ferry 1993). To limit back-diffusion, the anolyte flowed continuously (0.4 mL/min). Water oxidation to O₂ requires additional electron volts (> 1.23 V) and will produce chlorine gas (1.36 V) due to high overpotentials. The anode potential remained below the threshold for graphite oxidation (~–2.4V). O₂ and Cl₂ are not dissolved charge carriers. Water oxidation produced dissolved oxygen at saturation. Dissolved oxygen was not measurable in the cathode (Hach LDO10101, USA) and therefore was ignored for methane coulombic efficiency calculations (Van Eerten-Jansen et al. 2011). Chlorine gas was not measurable. Future operation with sea water would require trace chlorine gas removal to the anode, that is, alkali wet-scrubbing.

Figure 3 shows data from a set of potentiostatic measurements after 1 week of microbe acclimation, including the current densities and average, combined and final product coulombic efficiencies. The biocathode reduced CO₂ to CH₄

FIGURE 3 | Product coulombic efficiencies: Average and final (cathode) product coulombic efficiencies in the cathode and anode (CH₄, H₂ and VFA) (left y axis), the average current density (right y axis), and the cathode potential (x axis). Methane efficiency increased with more negative cathode potential and was optimal at –0.700 V SHE. The high current density and low coulombic efficiency at –0.550 and –0.600 V SHE indicates parasitic oxidation of VFA. VFA produced in the cathode is transported to the anode and oxidized. This was evidenced by measured VFA in the anode (open dots at –0.550 and –0.600 V) after the beginning of those tests, but not measurable by the end.

at efficiencies dependent upon the applied potential. Methane was co-produced with trace amounts of methanogenesis intermediates. The current density has a local maximum of –0.0782 A/m² at –0.550 V, which corresponds to VFA production with parasitic oxidation, then a plateau between –0.600 V and –0.750 V, and a global maximum at –0.800 V. The average coulombic efficiencies for methane and the intermediate products varied with applied potential. Methane and acetate were measured at less negative cathode potentials (–0.550 to –0.600 V) while methane and trace hydrogen (not shown) were measured at more negative cathode potentials (–0.600 to –0.800 V). Total average cathode product efficiency, detected in both the cathode and transported into the anode, initially decreased (–0.550 to –0.600 V) and then increased continuously from –0.650 V. In particular, the average VFA efficiency (primarily acetate, open dots) decreased to zero with more negative cathode potential (–0.550 to –0.600 V). The average methane efficiency initially decreased, proportional to the decreasing VFA, to a local minimum of 8% at –0.600 V, then continuously increased to 76% at –0.800 V. The intermediate and final methane efficiencies were different from the averages for the cathode and not measurable in the anode. In the –0.550 to –0.600 V range, the final cathode efficiency was lower than average. In the –0.650 to –0.800 V range, the final cathode efficiency was higher than average. The final methane efficiency was 95% at –0.700 V and remained high to –0.800 V.

Methane generation followed intermediate consumption or was co-produced with trace intermediates, indicating indirect electromethanogenesis. For cathode potentials between –0.550 and –0.650 V, a transition in intermediate from VFA (primarily acetate) to hydrogen is observed as the total average coulombic efficiency of the cathode followed the decreasing coulombic efficiency of the VFA and then increased with increasing co-production of trace hydrogen (Figure 3). Acetotrophic

methanogenesis is the most likely pathway for the potentials between -0.550V and -0.600V because methane production was proportional to and followed acetate production, which is typical in acetotrophic methanogenesis in AD (Ferry 1993). Indirect hydrogenotrophic electromethanogenesis is demonstrated between -0.650 and -0.800V because of the intermittent detection of hydrogen indicating consumption, similar to previous literature (Villano et al. 2010). It is common during hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis for the fast consumption rate of hydrogen to make direct hydrogen measurement impossible. Further, hydrogen was produced instead of methane when CO_2 was exhausted at the end of the measurement period, supporting the role of hydrogen as the intermediate in methane production. Hydrogen was measured at start-up (54%) before methane production for -0.800V with increased current density. The observed potentials and coulombic efficiencies are consistent with the literature values for acetate (Marshall 2013), formate (Lienemann et al. 2018) and hydrogenotrophic electromethanogenesis (Clauwaert et al. 2008; Van Eerten-Jansen et al. 2011; Villano et al. 2011). The observed current density, however, is lower than the average (1.56A/m^2) reported in literature.

Hydrogen was a more efficient intermediate than VFA (primarily acetate) due to differences in transport and utilization. VFA produced on the cathode (-0.550 and -0.600V) was transported

through the AEM to the anode and oxidized parasitically. Parasitic oxidation of cathode products artificially increased the current density, the energy efficiency and the voltage efficiency at -0.550 and -0.600V (see Table 2), while decreasing the cathode coulombic efficiency by an unknown amount. This explanation is supported by two observations. First, the presence of VFA in the anode and cathode was measured directly for the tests at -0.550V and -0.600V . The average total organic carbon (TOC) and total inorganic carbon (TIC) concentrations in the anode changed in proportion to one another initially when VFA was present, demonstrating they were transported together as would be expected during anion transport. Second, the coulombic efficiency of VFA at the anode was significant after the beginning of the measurements and negligible by the end, demonstrating VFA oxidation on the anode. Acetate can be isolated using a non-reactive anode or by placing a CEM/PEM before the anode (Gildemyn et al. 2015).

Figure 4 shows the CV evidence of the microbial catalysis of H_2 with the shift in the hydrogen overpotential tail from -0.9V , on bare graphite before inoculation, to -0.64V on the fully developed biofilm at the end of potentiostatic testing. The catalytic oxidation peaks on the return sweep from the hydrogen tail on the biofilm CV were correlated to the hydrogen tail, irreversible and most likely the oxidation of hydrogen. Double peaks (-0.4 to

TABLE 2 | Final potentiostatic production rates and efficiencies for biotic tests, rows 3–13, and abiotic tests, rows 15–18.

E_{we} (V SHE)	-0.500	-0.550	-0.600	-0.650	-0.700	-0.750	-0.800
Biotic tests							
I (A/m^2)		-0.089	-0.065	-0.066	-0.067	-0.071	-0.218
$r\text{CH}_4$ (moles/day)		$9.1\text{E-}6$	$1.7\text{E-}5$	$7.6\text{E-}5$	$1.3\text{E-}4$	$1.2\text{E-}4$	$2.6\text{E-}4$
$r\text{CH}_4$ ($\text{Nm}^3/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$)		0.0007	0.0012	0.0054	0.0094	0.0087	0.0187
$r\text{CO}_2$ transport (moles/ m^2/day)		0.093	0.191	0.192	0.360	0.530	0.125
$r\text{CO}_2$ transport ($\text{Nm}^3/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$)		0.11	0.23	0.23	0.43	0.64	0.15
Transport efficiency (% mol $\text{CO}_2/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$)		73	85	85	85	85	76
Coulombic efficiency (% CH_4)		7	13	60	96	83	95
Coulombic efficiency (% VFA)		2.8	2.5	0	0	0	0
Energy input ($\text{kWh}/\text{Nm}^3\text{CH}_4$)		9.2	13.8	14.9	15.5	15.3	16.3
Voltage efficiency (% $\text{CH}_4 + \text{VFA}$)		98	67	62	59	60	56
Energy efficiency (% $\text{CH}_4 + \text{VFA}$)		9	11	34	57	50	54
Abiotic tests							
Transport efficiency (% mol $\text{CO}_2/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$)	36		35		48		72
Transport efficiency (% mol $\text{CO}_2/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$) including cathode liquid absorption	58		64		85		90
$r\text{H}_2$ (moles/day)	$1.0\text{E-}4$		$1.5\text{E-}4$		$5.5\text{E-}4$		$1.1\text{E-}3$
$r\text{H}_2$ ($\text{Nm}^3/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$)	$7.4\text{E-}3$		$1.1\text{E-}2$		$3.9\text{E-}2$		$7.9\text{E-}2$

Note: t , time (years).

FIGURE 4 | Cyclic voltammograms: CVs of the uninoculated electrode (rod), non-turnover (0.2 to -1.1 V SHE) (black) and the final biofilm, turnover (0.2 to -0.8 V SHE) (red) at 1 mV/s. Microbes catalyzed the reduction of the hydrogen overpotential, evidenced by the shift in the hydrogen tail from -0.9 V SHE to -0.7 V SHE. The two catalytic oxidation peaks of the biofilm are presumably hydrogen oxidation.

FIGURE 5 | Potentiostatic test of cathode intermediate at -0.700 V SHE: Shows the reduction of CO_2 in the gas headspace from above the natural gas pipeline CO_2 limit to below it, steady current and methane production over 2 days. The drop in current density at the end marks the CO_2 supply shut off. H_2 gas production increased in response ($< 1\%$, not shown), proving intermediate H_2 .

-0.6 V) are characteristic of geobacter species, a known electroactive microbe that commonly has syntrophic interactions with methanogens. Biohydrogen is the most common intermediate in literature (Call, Wagner, and Logan 2009; Clauwaert et al. 2008; Morozov et al. 2002; Rozendal et al. 2008a; Rozendal et al. 2008b; Tartakovsky et al. 2014; Van Eerten-Jansen et al. 2011; Villano et al. 2011).

Figure 5 shows the removal of CO_2 was possible to below typical natural gas pipeline limits (2% vol.) within 6 h of operation. Measurements were obtained with intentionally low CO_2 (4% vol.) to simultaneously test for trace intermediates and absorption limits. The reduction of carbon dioxide, production of methane, and the current density are shown as a function of time at -0.700 V. The current density was approximately constant during continuous operation with CO_2 gas recirculation and decreased rapidly when the CO_2 was exhausted and the HCO_3^- depleted

FIGURE 6 | Transport efficiencies: The average bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) transport efficiencies from the cathode to anode (left y axis), and average CO_2 converted to methane in the cathode (right y axis), versus the cathode potential (x axis). Ideal biotic transport efficiency is 88.8% (dashed line). Microbial catalysis increased current density and transport efficiency above that of abiotic (H_2) tests. At -0.800 V SHE, transport efficiency decreased (75%) when methane production increased, indicating HCO_3^- limitation, due to rate limiting CO_2 absorption.

at 50 h (star). The coulombic efficiency for hydrogen production increased rapidly to 0.40% (0.1% vol. not shown) when the carbon dioxide supply was depleted, demonstrating hydrogen was the electrocatalytically reduced intermediate to methane production, agreeing with previous research (Villano et al. 2011). Methane was measurably produced within 10 h and statistically significant by ~ 24 h. The production of pipeline standard methane from biogas demonstrates an effective means of purification for small scale biogas streams. This method can achieve lower CO_2 concentrations than standard equipment, which are limited by thermodynamic absorption limits ($\sim 2\%$).

Figure 6 shows bicarbonate transport efficiency data for the biotic tests with conversion of CO_2 to CH_4 and the abiotic control tests over the range of potentials. Removal of CO_2 was possible to below typical pipeline specifications (i.e., typically $< 2\%$ CO_2) over the range of cathode potentials and current densities provided sufficient residence time. High purity will require precise control of inlet gas and current density. Abiotic transport control tests demonstrated increased transport efficiencies with increased electromotive force (EMF), as expected. Abiotic transport efficiency reached 72% (mol $\text{CO}_2/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$) by -0.800 V, significantly lower than biotic transport efficiency. Abiotic transport efficiency, including the absorbed HCO_3^- awaiting transport, approached the ideal biotic limit (88%) by -0.700 V (85% mol $\text{CO}_2/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$). Biotic transport efficiency approached the ideal biotic limit by -0.600 V (84.7% mol $\text{CO}_2/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$) and remained relatively constant until -0.800 V, where it became limited by HCO_3^- availability. The biotic conversion of CO_2 to CH_4 shows increased methane generation with more negative cathode potential, with a minima at -0.550 V ($\sim 0.5\%$) and maxima at -0.800 V (12%). Methane production decreased slightly (-0.700 to -0.750 V), due to CO_2 absorption limits. For this study saturation was possible (-0.550 to -0.750 V), however absorption remained the rate limiting transport step. Absorption was increased with gas recirculation, which increased the bubble residence time. The transport

of ions with less than one CO_2 per charge (e.g., CO_3^{2-}) or non- CO_2 ions (e.g., OH^- or Cl^-) reduced the transport efficiency of HCO_3^- . The transport of ions with more than one carbon per charge (e.g., CH_3COO^-) increased the transport efficiency of carbon and CO_2 gas depletion rate, despite decreasing the transport efficiency of HCO_3^- . Solution conductivity less than saturation (HCO_3^-) reduced current density and increased salt transport.

Hydrogen production drives abiotic transport of HCO_3^- and is ideally 100% ($\text{mol CO}_2/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$). HCO_3^- transport does not compete with conversion to CH_4 without microbes. HCO_3^- transport efficiency was lower for abiotic tests than for biotic, despite sufficient CO_2 , because of the high H_2 reaction overpotential and lower current density.

Methane production drives the biotic transport of HCO_3^- , which is ideally 88% ($\text{mol CO}_2/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$). Microbial catalysis increased the current density and HCO_3^- transport efficiency of biotic tests above that of abiotic (H_2) by 3%–40%. Acetate production and its parasitic oxidation (-0.550 to -0.600V) led to decreased methane production ($\sim 0.5\%$ mol CO_2), while maintaining increased HCO_3^- transport efficiency, greater than abiotic transport. Acetate production removes the same amount of carbon from biogas, however the acetate is transported through the AEM. The optimal potential for energy efficient biotic HCO_3^- transport is -0.600V , which includes acetate production.

Biotic HCO_3^- transport efficiency remained high until -0.800V (75% $\text{mol CO}_2/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$), where the current density increased, and the CO_2 supply could no longer support transport. The competition for HCO_3^- between methane production and transport resulted in increased methane production ($\sim 12\%$ $\text{mol CO}_2/\text{day}$), decreased HCO_3^- mass (75%) and coulombic transport efficiency, and increased anion salt transport instead of HCO_3^- . Ideal HCO_3^- transport efficiency (88%) was achieved after supplying additional CO_2 (not shown).

Table 2 shows the final data set for the biotic and abiotic potentiostatic measurements and controls, including methane production, HCO_3^- transport rates and efficiencies. The most energy efficient operation was at -0.700V based on the highest

methane coulombic efficiency and voltage efficiency. Reducing the optimal potential to less than -0.700V may be possible if microbe acclimation is prolonged (1 month versus 1 week).

Fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) analysis confirmed the transition of the microbial community of the original culture and final culture (Figure 7). The original culture was dominated by Archaea (ARC915, green) and methanosarcinales (MSMX860, blue), which includes both acetotrophic and hydrogenotrophic methanogens, and some methanosaetaceae (MX825, red), which are obligate acetotrophs. Methanosaetaceae are common in UASB granules and not surprising since UASB granules were used in the inoculum. The final culture was dominated by methanosarcinales (MSMX860, blue) with less Archaea domain (ARC915, green) and trace methanosaetaceae (MX825, red). Results conclude the culture was dominated by autotrophic methanogens, as they were not acetotrophs. Microbes were selected from well fed regions at pH7. Conclusions may not hold for the range of BES conditions tested, as communities change with environmental conditions. The methanogenic species present in anaerobic digestion is a key predictor to shifts in the preceding microbial population (Batstone and Virdis 2014) and could be studied further in combination with experimental setup (pH, galvanic operation, etc.). Low electrode resistance and cost-effective scale-up could be possible if microbes were capable of using alternating current.

High pressure improves performance by driving CO_2 absorption to its maximum value. The gas absorption coefficient of CO_2 in water is greater than CH_4 , therefore high pressure dissolves more CO_2 than CH_4 . Saturation improves HCO_3^- ion transport efficiency by maintaining high HCO_3^- concentration over salts, decreases the mass transport resistance, and reduces reactor volume and energy use (Eisaman et al. 2011; Strathmann 2004). Absorption capacity could be increased using a more basic pH (7.5–8), which favors CO_2 ionization and buffers alkali pH changes during cathodic operation; however, this is the upper pH limit of methanogen operation. Absorption rates could be increased using lower temperature ($< 30^\circ\text{C}$), however the rate of methanogenesis decreases at lower temperature. Biogas pressure of 10bar will increase CO_2 absorption to $\sim 90\%$ before removal by the BES and electrochemical transport, thus driving

FIGURE 7 | Biofilm FISH images: FISH images of cathode granules of original incubation culture (a, left) and final culture (b, right), showing the transition in microbial population to methanosarcinales.

high transport rates with low energy. The purified methane will be pressurized for transport and sale.

High consumption rates of hydrogen gas by any microbe improves the coulombic efficiency of hydrogen electrolysis and accelerates the production rates of methane or acetate. CO₂ conversion is a non-spontaneous reaction with a negative potential (V). The standard redox potential of CO₂/acetate is -0.29 V and CO₂/CH₄ is -0.24 V vs. SHE at pH 7. Low H₂ partial pressure can favor hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis, over hydrogenotrophic acetogenesis at $E^\circ(\text{H}^+/\text{H}_2) = -0.296 \text{ V}$ at pH 7, 25°C and 10⁻⁴ atm, not the standard -0.414 V (Ferry 1992; Ferry 1993). The Nernst equation Equation (4) below calculates the actual reduction reaction potential as the standard potential minus the adjustment for real temperature, pressure and concentration. A logarithm of the reaction ratio (quotient) less than 1 results in a less negative potential. Increasing the reactant CO₂ concentration (or partial pressure or activity) and maintaining high consumption rates of hydrogen gas by microbes will reduce the magnitude of the negative potential, resulting in less electrical energy required to achieve the same conversion,

$$E(V) = E^\circ - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left(\frac{[\text{Reduced Product}]^b}{[\text{Oxidized Reactant}]^a} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$E(V) = -0.24 - \frac{RT}{8F} \ln \left(\frac{[\text{CH}_4]^1}{[\text{CO}_2]^1} \right)$$

4 | Conclusions

Biogas is a global methane resource that is underutilized due to the variable methane content and requires purification to pipeline grade natural gas (98% methane) to receive maximum value. Small biogas streams were targeted for purification along with further reduction in wastewater effluent organics (COD) to safer levels for release to the ocean and Great Barrier Reef. These resources are otherwise financially unrecoverable with current technology. A bioelectrochemical system was designed to combine biogas purification (cathode) with the removal of the trace organics (COD) from wastewater (anode). Experiments evaluated the influence of cathode potential on bicarbonate (CO₂) removal and continuous pure methane production. This is one of the first BES designs specifically for biogas purification using an AEM with HCO₃⁻ transport. Purification was achieved to pipeline standards (≥ 98%). Results demonstrated the BES is capable of biogas purification in two ways. First, the migration of HCO₃⁻ (8/9 mol) through the AEM completes the circuit, thus balancing the charge and achieving electroneutrality. Second, the simultaneous conversion of CO₂ to CH₄ (1/9 mol) uses biocatalytically produced intermediates hydrogen and volatile fatty acids. Over the range of potentials, microbes bioelectrochemically converted (reduced) 0.5 to 12% (ideal 11%) of the CO₂. The remaining CO₂ was removed by transport, 73% to 85% (ideal 89%). The optimal potential was -0.700 V with 96% methane coulombic efficiency. Transporting HCO₃⁻ decreased the power required to purify biogas on a molar basis.

A techno-economic analysis (TEA) was done to prove the financial viability of this process to industry for small biogas streams (< 8.85 GJ/h), with an energy ratio similar to commercial equipment,

0.064 (kWh-e/kWh CH₄). Results demonstrate membrane costs dominate the capital investment of \$677,000 to \$867,000 USD\$ for the scaled-up BES plant. A payback period of less than 10 years is viable using the wholesale price of methane with graphite granules, SS wool or graphite felt. The AEM process was more energy efficient than the CEM because the operating energy of an AEM was eight times less than a CEM on a per mole basis and 3.6× less on an energy per volume basis, 0.65 versus 2.4 kWh/Nm³ CH₄. This demonstrates the energetic and financial advantage of HCO₃⁻ anion transport over complete CO₂ conversion. For the purpose of biogas purification, CEM operation required more energy (cost) than AEM to purify the same amount of biogas. Converting all the carbon dioxide to methane (CEM) was energy inefficient and reduced profitability. The increased capex and opex were not offset by the small increase in methane sales. Bulk methane prices will need to be > 10× greater to justify CEM operation.

The TEA model of the BES demonstrated the capital and operating costs for purifying biogas from an UASB. See Table S3 for further information (Mueller Klein 2024). To purify the output of an average single UASB, 1000 m³/day wastewater, the BES throughput capacity would be 100 Nm³/h biogas (67:33 CH₄:CO₂) generating an output of 70.5 Nm³/h compressed methane (7.5 atm), which produces 62.7 GJ/d (59.7 mcf/day) energy (Tchobanoglous 2003). The TEA model's current density was 10 A/m² [33–35] at 0.7 V (cell) with indirect electromethanogenesis at the cathode (-0.9 V) and trace wastewater organic oxidation at the anode (-0.2 V) (Rabaey and Rozendal 2010; Rozendal et al. 2006). Direct electromethanogenesis (-0.24 V) will produce the ideal power efficiency, however it has not yet been proven for small scale production and was not modeled. The model assumed a balanced charge transfer of HCO₃⁻. Grid power supplied the energy difference. Off-grid power could be supplied by solar panels.

The operating energy ratio of the BES model was comparable to current industrial technologies for small scale applications (0.064 kWh-e/kWh CH₄) (Table 3). Commercial purification equipment operates via pressure or thermal absorption. This BES operated at ambient pressure and compressed the output to pipeline pressure (7.5 atm). Operating a high-pressure BES

TABLE 3 | Operating energy for biogas purification technologies per kWh CH₄.

Biogas purification process	Electrical energy (kWh-e/kWh CH ₄)	Heat energy (kWh/kWh CH ₄)
Water scrubber ^a	0.061	
Amine scrubber ^a	0.027	0.112
PSA ^a	0.061	
Membrane ^a	0.061	
Organic solvent scrubber ^a	0.057	
BES ^b	0.064	
Electrolyzer ^c	1.74	

^aBauer et al. (2013), Urban (2009).

^bThis study.

^cVerde (2009).

improves energy efficiency (Eisaman et al. 2011). High-pressure operation was modeled in the TEA calculations and improved payback time by at least 1 year in all scenarios.

Table 4 shows the calculated capex and opex of the BES models using carbon granules or felt (Coulson et al. 2006). The capital and payback period of the model was less than 10 years, within the financial range of industry. The capital and operating costs used a deterministic calculation based on the material cost of the membrane and electrodes (innards) as 60% of the total unit cost and a profit of 493 USD\$/day (Table 4). Carbon granules, felt, plates and SS 434 wool were compared as the cheapest viable options (Table S2). The overnight fixed capital cost (FCC) for the complete physical plant was \$677,000 to \$867,000 USD depending on the electrode material, carbon granules or graphite felt.

For the pure Methane BES, the payback period was 7 years for carbon granules, 10.5 years for carbon felt and 8 years for SS 434 wool. Operating the methane BES at greater than 7 atm reduced the payback period by 1 to 2 years for all scenarios. Acetate is a feedstock substitute for petroleum hydrocarbons and more profitable than methane. For the Acetate BES, the payback period was 8 years for carbon granules, 11 years for felt, and 8 years for SS 434 wool. The Acetate BES produced slightly less methane (67 Nm³/h). Once constructed, the methane BES would take 1 month minimum to attain full capacity for biofilm growth and quality control testing. Operating costs assume a life of 30 years and the primary maintenance cost would be the replacement of membranes every 1.1 Mm³ wastewater (2.6 MNm³ biogas) or about once every 3 years. Fixed operating costs (FOC) were assumed at 10% of the fixed capital cost and no leverage (debt) was assumed.

The membrane cost dominated the capex, which dominated the payback period. The anion exchange membrane cost constituted 75%–97% of the capital cost. Alternatively, the alleviated fuel cost could be used if the compressed methane is used for transportation fuel, which would result in a shorter payback period given transport fuels are usually a greater price per kJ than natural gas. Struvite was not included in the model; the market price ranged from 280 to 350 USD\$/ton Muys et al. 2021. The energy used by an AEM was eight times less than a CEM on a per mole basis.

Scale-up uses stacked electrodes in parallel or serpentine cross-flow, 1–2 cm wide. Parallel cross-flow requires multiple pressure control valves. Carbon felt is preferable as it provides lower electrode resistance and void volume, higher surface area and shorter electrode spacing. Steel wool may be ideal for cathodes if corrosion is avoided. Degassing uses flash columns. For additional resources (Noori et al. 2020; Vielstich, Lamm, and Gasteiger 2003).

The primary financial and physical challenge for the BES, as for all electrochemical systems, is achieving high current density. Increasing current density increases production capacity without increasing equipment size. Industrial electrolyzers operate at 1000–10,000 A/m² at high voltage and therefore high cost. Bulk phase biomethanation with industrial electrolyzers was capital cost prohibitive (Vorrath 2018). Low cost electrolyzers would improve return on investment.

TABLE 4 | Capital investment table and proforma income statement (Coulson et al. 2006).

Capital and operating costs \$USD	Carbon granules	Carbon felt
Cost of membrane unit innards	\$ 110,000	\$ 141,000
Fraction of innards in total cost	0.6	0.6
Total BES unit cost	\$ 183,000	\$ 234,000
Equipment build	0.4	0.4
Piping	0.7	0.7
Instrumentation	0.2	0.2
Electrical	0.1	0.1
Buildings	0.15	0.15
Sum of capital fees	2.55	2.55
Total physical plant cost	\$ 467,000	\$ 598,000
Design/engineering fees	0.3	0.3
EPC fees	0.05	0.05
Contingency	0.1	0.1
Sum of construction fees	1.45	1.45
Fixed, overnight capital cost (FCC)	\$ 677,000	\$ 867,000
% of FCC (\$/pa)	0.1	0.1
Discount rate	0.1	0.1
Fixed operating costs (FOC)	\$ 68,000	\$ 87,000
Total revenue for the Methane BES		
Natural Gas \$/GJ	\$ 7.40	\$ 7.40
Electricity \$/kWh	(\$ 0.0534)	(\$ 0.0534)
Compressed CO ₂ (99.95%) \$/kg	\$ 0.056	\$ 0.056
Struvite* (not included) \$/ton	\$ 280–\$ 350	\$ 280–\$ 350
Revenue \$/day	\$ 493	\$ 493
Revenue \$/year	\$ 171,000	\$ 171,000
Total revenue for the Acetate BES		
Natural gas \$/GJ	\$ 7.40	\$ 7.40
Electricity \$/kWh	(\$ 0.0534)	(\$ 0.0534)
Compressed CO ₂ (99.95%) \$/kg	\$ 0.056	\$ 0.056
Acetic acid \$/kg	\$ 0.585	\$ 0.585
Revenue \$/day	\$ 592	\$ 592
Revenue \$/year	\$ 205,000	\$ 205,000

*Struvite was not included in revenue, price reference only (Ueno and Fujii 2001).

Follow up studies include (1) high pressure operation; (2) long term operation; (3) high current density operation, ideal for industry because it eliminates the reference electrode (subject to failure); (4) catalysts to enhance microbial catalysis (ex. Ni, Fe, enzymes) [60, 67]; (5) detailed tests to determine the identity of electrocatalytic microbial populations; (6) operation with a magnesium anode for net energy production and struvite and MgCO₃ precipitate recovery; (7) reactor redesign to reduce membrane requirements or price in scale up; (8) operation with industrial electrolyzers under high pressure with methanogenic microbes in the bulk liquid.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The supporting data for this paper is available for download both at the EU archive site zenodo link here and as a supporting document with the published paper, <https://zenodo.org/>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1328634>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13286341>, <https://zenodo.org/records/13286342>.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.